

Figure 7. Descriptions for changes made to ToxRTool with limitations and considerations included.			
Changes Made	Description	Limitation	Other Considerations
1. modified all the question(s)	Authors modified all the questions for the 5 groupings listed (Test Substance Identification, Test System Characterization, etc.).	Adds new terminology and elements to the original 2009 questions. 2. Changes what may be considered the Red Criteria.	Consolidated notes from reviewers
2. met original questions with modifications	Authors use the original 2009 questions, but specify modifications to certain questions for the 5 groupings listed (Test Substance Identification, Test System Characterization, etc.).	Additions may be specific to the field of study or topic only so limited generalization.	Consolidated notes from reviewers
3. added a question(s)	Authors add one or more questions for the 5 groupings listed (Test Substance Identification, Test System Characterization, etc.).	Changes what may be considered the Red Criteria and requires a new scoring system.	Consolidated notes from reviewers
4. added a new "Criteria Group"	Authors added a new 'Criteria Group' based on their field of study or topic for the 5 groupings listed (Test Substance Identification, Test System Characterization, etc.).	Introduces different data groupings which may alter interpretation of the results	Consolidated notes from reviewers
5. developed a new scoring system	Authors developed a scoring system different from the 2009 publication 5 groupings listed (Test Substance Identification, Test System Characterization, etc.).	Comparison between studies will vary unless scientists in the field of study all agree with the changes.	Consolidated notes from reviewers
6. none (not mentioned or addressed)	Authors did not may any other changes or nothing else was mentioned in the original 5 groupings listed (Test Substance Identification, Test System Characterization, etc.).	N/A	N/A
Figure 7. Descriptions for changes made to ToxRTool with limitations and considerations included. The numbers included for each change will be used in Table 5 so frequencies can be totaled.			